

Synthesis of uranium(IV) complexes of Schiff bases

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Uranium(IV) complexes with Schiff bases formed by condensation of 3-substituted-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole and substituted-salicylaldehyde have been synthesized in dry benzene under nitrogen atmosphere. A coordination number eight is suggested for these uranium(IV) complexes with cubic geometry.

Much work has been done on the actinide metal complexes¹, however the coordination chemistry of uranium(IV) complexes has received little attention. In continuation of our work on actinide metal complexes²⁻⁴ with various ligands, we report herein the synthesis of uranium(IV) complexes with biologically active 3-substituted-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole Schiff bases.

Ligand	R	R'	Ligand	R	R'
L ¹ H ₂	H	H	L ⁹ H ₂	C ₂ H ₅	H
L ² H ₂	H	CH ₃	L ¹⁰ H ₂	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃
L ³ H ₂	H	Cl	L ¹¹ H ₂	C ₂ H ₅	Cl
L ⁴ H ₂	H	OCH ₃	L ¹² H ₂	C ₂ H ₅	OCH ₃
L ⁵ H ₂	CH ₃	H	L ¹³ H ₂	C ₃ H ₇	H
L ⁶ H ₂	CH ₃	CH ₃	L ¹⁴ H ₂	C ₃ H ₇	CH ₃
L ⁷ H ₂	CH ₃	Cl	L ¹⁵ H ₂	C ₃ H ₇	Cl
L ⁸ H ₂	CH ₃	OCH ₃	L ¹⁶ H ₂	C ₃ H ₇	OCH ₃

Results and Discussion

The uranium(IV) complexes [U(LH)₂(OAc)₂] are greenish in colour. The analytical data of the complexes indicate metal-to-ligand ratio to be 1 : 2. The conductivity data of the complexes in 10⁻³ M DMF (17–30 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) show that they are non-electrolytes. Their magnetic moments (2.76–3.06 B.M.) agree with the presence of two unpaired electrons⁵ and excludes the possibility of metal-metal interaction suggesting a cubic geometry. The slow decrease in μ_{eff} values observed with increase in time indicates, slow oxidation of U^{IV} to U^{VI}; this process is fast in atmospheric

air compared to in vacuo.

The free ligands exist in thione-thiol tautomeric forms⁶ as indicated by the presence of bands at 3200 (NH), 2400–2300 (SH), 2700–2600 (intramolecular H-bonded OH), 1640–1620 (azomethine C=N), 1280 (phenolic C–O) and 760–740 cm⁻¹ (C=S).

In the complexes, the band due to H-bonded OH of the ligands disappeared and phenolic C–O vibrations appeared at 1315–1310 cm⁻¹ region. This indicates coordination of the ligand phenolic OH to U^{IV} through oxygen via deprotonation⁷. The ligand band due to azomethine C=N shifted to lower frequency (1610 cm⁻¹) suggesting the coordination of C=N group through its nitrogen⁸. The ligand band due to C=S remained unperturbed in the complexes, suggesting non-involvement of sulfur atom of mercapto group in coordination⁹ and this is reflected by the bands due to NH and SH vibrations appearing in the same region as in the case of ligand. The ν_{asy}(OCO) (ν₈) and ν_{sym}(OCO) (ν₃) bands of acetate modes appeared around 1555 and 1485 cm⁻¹, and the band separation of ν₃ and ν₈ (Δν = ~70 cm⁻¹) suggests that acetate moieties are coordinated in a chelating bidentate fashion¹⁰ in these U^{IV} complexes. All these observations suggest that the ligands behave as monobasic bidentate ligands by coordinating through azomethine nitrogen atom and oxygen atom of phenolic OH. The bands at 590–630 and 500–550 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ν_{U–N} and ν_{U–O} vibrations, respectively^{3,4}.

Gans *et al.*¹¹ studied the reflectance spectra of a series of uranium(IV) complexes and divided them into three classes based on intensities of the bands on the arbitrary scale as 'weak intensity spectra', 'medium intensity spectra' and 'strong intensity spectra'. Based on this classification and the band positions (Table 1) of the present uranium(IV) complexes, it is suggested that the spectra belong to the 'strong intensity' type and resemble with those of eight-coordinated uranium(IV) complexes with cubic geometry^{4,11,12}. This suggests coordination number eight for the present complexes.

Table 1. Reflectance spectral data of uranium(IV) complexes in nm

Term	[U(L ⁵ H) ₂ (OAc) ₂]	[U(L ⁹ H) ₂ (OAc) ₂]
³ F ₂	1955	1950
	1885	1915
	1870	1890
	1860	–
³ H ₅	1535	1495
	1405	1385
³ F ₃	1170	1170
³ F ₄	1070	1065
³ H ₆	805	800
³ P ₀	650	645
¹ G ₄	630	635
¹ D ₂	590	–
³ P ₁	–	580
³ I ₆	460	470
³ P ₂	430	440
	425	–

Experimental

The chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Substituted salicylaldehydes¹³, and 3-substituted-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole¹⁴ and their Schiff bases⁶ were prepared according to reported methods. Uranium(IV) acetate was prepared¹⁵ by the reduction of uranyl acetate with zinc amalgam.

The complexes of uranium acetate with Schiff bases were prepared by refluxing uranium(IV) acetate (0.01 mol) and the ligand (0.02 mol) in dry benzene under nitrogen atmosphere with constant stirring for ~3 h. The complexes separated were washed with dry benzene, dried and stored under vacuum over P₂O₅.

The complexes were analysed for metal and sulfur by standard methods¹⁶ and nitrogen by Duma's method. The conductance was measured in DMF solvent on an Elico CM 82 conductivity bridge. The magnetic measurements at room temperature were made on Gouy balance. IR spectra were recorded on a Nicolet 170SX spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Cary-d-2390 spectrophotometer.

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